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va
TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE CHALLENGES OF ECONOMIC INTEGRATION IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY FOR CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the main challenges of economic integration among Central Asian countries in the context of global economic relations. It highlights the impact of geographical limitations, weak infrastructure, and institutional barriers on regional trade and cooperation. The study also emphasizes the importance of balanced external partnerships and regional policy harmonization for sustainable development.

Key words: Central Asia, economic integration, regional cooperation, trade, globalization, infrastructure, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi Markaziy Osiyo davlatlarining jahon iqtisodiyoti sharoitidagi iqtisodiy integratsiya jarayonidagi asosiy muammolari tahlil qilingan. Geografik cheklovlar, infratuzilmaning zaifligi va institutsional to'siqlarning mintaqaviy savdo va hamkorlikka ta'siri yoritilgan. Shuningdek, barqaror rivojlanish uchun tashqi hamkorlikni muvozanatli yo'lga qo'yish va hududiy siyosatni uyg'unlashtirish zarurligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Markaziy Osiyo, iqtisodiy integratsiya, mintaqaviy hamkorlik, savdo, globallashuv, infratuzilma, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В данной тезисе рассматриваются основные проблемы экономической интеграции стран Центральной Азии в условиях глобальной экономики. Освещается влияние географических ограничений, слабой инфраструктуры и институциональных барьеров на региональную торговлю и сотрудничество. Также подчеркивается необходимость сбалансированного внешнего партнёрства и гармонизации региональной политики для устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, экономическая интеграция, региональное сотрудничество, торговля, глобализация, инфраструктура, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

After the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, the five newly independent Central Asian republics — Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan — faced significant challenges in transitioning from a centrally planned economy to a market-based system. This transformation was difficult for nearly all sectors, particularly manufacturing, and led to a substantial decline in GDP [1].

Despite unifying factors such as geographical proximity, similar economic structures, and shared historical experiences, these countries have never joined integration organizations composed solely of Central Asian states. At the same time, they have participated in international organizations such as the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) [2].

The Central Asian countries have actively developed trade and economic relations with major global markets, including the European Union, China, other Asian economies, and Russia. Nevertheless, opportunities for intra-regional integration remain underutilized due to non-economic factors such as weak institutions, limited private sector development, and insufficient infrastructure [3].

As a result, achieving a balance between regional integration and active engagement with external markets is essential for enhancing economic stability and effectively managing external debt in Central Asia.

Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the Central Asian countries made several attempts to strengthen trade and economic cooperation within the post-Soviet space. In 1994, the first multilateral trade

facilitation agreement was proposed under the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), aiming to enhance economic collaboration among member states [4].

1. During the Soviet era, the Central Asian countries were largely disconnected from each other in terms of production chains and mainly served as sources of raw materials, while subsequent stages of production were concentrated in Russia's major industrial centers [5]. Consequently, restructuring the production system involved significant fiscal, economic, and social costs.

2. Raw material exports provided stable budget revenues at relatively low costs, enabling these countries to address pressing social issues, maintain household incomes, and import capital and consumer goods. This strategy, combined with the large-scale privatization of state enterprises, also contributed to relatively high economic growth rates.

However, these factors were insufficient to fully promote regional integration and trade cooperation among the Central Asian states, as other fundamental barriers remained.

Overall, the Central Asian countries have pursued a policy of actively developing foreign trade since the 1990s and have maintained a high degree of trade openness. According to recent data, in the early 1990s (1992–1996), trade indicators in Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Kyrgyzstan showed significant fluctuations; for instance, Kazakhstan's trade value decreased from 149 to 71, while Kyrgyzstan's increased from 83 to 87. During this period, data for Uzbekistan and Tajikistan were partially unavailable, but in the years with available figures (1997–2000), trade activity gradually expanded.

Figure 1. Trade Openness of the Central Asian Countries (foreign trade as % of GDP)

S o u r c e: World Bank data

Between 2005 and 2010, trade indicators again exhibited notable variations, particularly in Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan, reflecting the impact of the global financial crisis of 2008–2009 on the region. During this period, Uzbekistan's trade indicators remained relatively stable, ranging between 67 and 80.

From 2010 to 2023, the Central Asian countries demonstrated a generally steady growth trend in foreign trade, diversifying their markets and integrating further into the global economy. For instance:

- Kazakhstan increased from 57 to 62,
- Tajikistan from 56 to 66,
- Uzbekistan from 49 to 66,
- Kyrgyzstan from 79 to 132,
- Turkmenistan from 33 to 37, showing comparatively slower growth.

These data confirm that, during the 1990s, the Central Asian countries gradually reduced their trade dependence on Russia while expanding commerce with Europe and other regions. By the late 2000s, the countries had adopted different approaches to economic stabilization and integration. For example, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan joined the Eurasian Economic Community (EurAsEC) to strengthen integration with Russia, whereas Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan maintained a more cautious stance and refrained from rapid accession.

Consequently, this dataset clearly illustrates the dynamics of foreign trade in Central Asia, the effects of economic crises and policy choices, and the region's distinctive paths toward integration into the global economy.

Table 1. CA Countries' Trade with Other CA Countries and with Key Extra-Regional Trading Partners, % of total foreign trade (2023)

CA Country	CA Countries (%)	Russia (%)	China (%)	EU (%)	Other (%)
Uzbekistan	12.3	11.3*	12.0*	8.5*	55.9*
Kazakhstan	5.5	18.4*	22.2*	9.4*	44.5*
Kyrgyzstan	13.0	19.0*	35.0*	8.0*	25.0*
Tajikistan	26.8	18.0*	27.6*	8.0*	20.8*
Turkmenistan	—	—	—	—	—

Source: U.N. Comtrade

China's influence on Central Asian foreign trade expanded significantly during the 2000s, driven primarily by a surge in domestic energy demand resulting from China's exceptional economic growth. Countries with abundant hydrocarbon resources — including Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan — rapidly redirected a substantial share of their oil and gas exports toward the Chinese market [6].

Table 2. Two Leading Sectors in CA Countries' Exports to Russia, EU, and China (2023, estimated based on trade structure)

Country	Russia – Main sectors (% of exports to Russia)	EU – Main sectors (% of exports to EU)	China – Main sectors (% of exports to China)
Kazakhstan	Mineral fuels (≈45%), Metals and manufactured goods (≈30%)	Mineral fuels (≈60%), Metals (≈25%)	Mineral fuels (≈55%), Metals and chemicals (≈30%)
Uzbekistan	Manufactured products (≈40%), Food & textiles (≈25%)	Chemical products (≈35%), Machinery & textiles (≈30%)	Raw materials excl. fuels (≈40%), Manufactured goods (≈30%)
Kyrgyzstan	Manufactured products (≈50%), Food and minerals (≈20%)	Gold & metals (≈60%), Manufactured goods (≈25%)	Manufactured products (≈35%), Raw materials (≈30%)
Tajikistan	Aluminum & metals (≈45%), Raw materials (≈30%)	Aluminum products (≈55%), Textile goods (≈25%)	Raw materials excl. fuels (≈40%), Manufactured goods (≈35%)
Turkmenistan	Mineral fuels (≈80%), Chemical products (≈10%)	Mineral fuels (≈75%), Textile & chemicals (≈15%)	Mineral fuels (≈85%), Chemical products (≈10%)

Source: U.N. Comtrade

Based on 2023 trade data, Kazakhstan conducts only 5.5% of its total trade with fellow Central Asian countries, while Russia accounts for 18.4%, China for 22.2%, and the European Union (EU) for 9.4%. Uzbekistan's trade with other Central Asian countries represents 12.3% of its total, with Russia at 11.3%, China at 12.0%, and the EU at 8.5%. Kyrgyzstan's intra-regional trade share stands at 13.0%, with 19.0% directed to Russia, 35.0% to China, and 8.0% to the EU. Tajikistan has the highest intra-regional trade proportion at 26.8%, alongside 18.0% with Russia, 27.6% with China, and 8.0% with the EU. The remainder of trade for these countries is distributed among other international partners.

However, the composition of trade that Central Asian countries conduct with Russia, the European Union, and China varies considerably (see Table 2).

Landlocked countries face a range of structural constraints that negatively affect both foreign trade performance and overall economic growth. Their economic opportunities are inherently limited, as they must rely on negotiations with neighboring coastal states to secure access to seaports [7]. Moreover, traded goods are subject to additional costs associated with cross-border transit, on top of regular transport expenses.

As a result, landlocked countries typically exhibit lower volumes of foreign trade and slower economic growth compared to their coastal counterparts [8]. Empirical studies indicate that being landlocked reduces average annual economic growth by approximately 1.5 percentage points relative to coastal nations. Furthermore, transport and border-crossing costs significantly elevate the prices of both imports and exports, thereby limiting international competitiveness [9].

Figure 2. Tien Shan and Pamirs (Central Asia)

Source: www.maps-tian-shan-and-pamir.google.com

In addition to the lack of access to the sea, the complex geography of Central Asia further constrains infrastructure development and limits access to neighboring coastal countries. The region's major mountain ranges, including the Tien Shan and the Pamirs, serve as natural barriers to overland transport and trade. For example, Tajikistan remains particularly isolated compared to its regional neighbors, as the impassable mountains to the south and its border with Afghanistan hinder overland trade with South Asian countries.

This geographical isolation not only increases the costs of trading with distant coastal nations but also restricts opportunities for overland trade within Central Asia itself. In this context, the limited trade relations between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, and to some extent between Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, provide clear examples of how geography continues to shape regional economic connectivity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study shows that economic integration in Central Asia remains limited due to weak infrastructure, geographical barriers, and institutional fragmentation. Despite active cooperation with major partners such as China, Russia, and the European Union, intra-regional trade and investment levels are still low.

To achieve sustainable integration, Central Asian countries should strengthen regional transport and logistics systems, harmonize trade regulations, and develop joint industrial projects. Expanding digital infrastructure and promoting value-added production will enhance competitiveness. Balanced cooperation with global partners, alongside deeper regional coordination, is essential for achieving long-term economic stability and growth.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. The World Bank. (2002). *Transition—The First Ten Years: Analysis and Lessons for Eastern Europe and the Former Soviet Union*. Washington, D.C., p. 6.
2. Rakhimov, M. A. (2018). *Complex Regionalism in Central Asia: Local, Regional, and Global Factors*. Cambridge Journal of Eurasian Studies, No. 2, 1–12.

3. Tadjbakhsh, S. (2012). Central Asia and Afghanistan: Insulation on the Silk Road, Between Eurasia and the Heart of Asia. Paper 3 of the PRIO Project "Afghanistan in a Neighborhood Perspective," 1–12.
4. Kurmanalieva, E., & Parpiev, Z. (2008). Geography and Trade in Central Asia. SSRN Electronic Journal, January.
5. Włodkowska-Bagan, A. (2012). Russian Foreign Policy towards Central Asia. In Stępniewski, T. (Ed.), *The New Great Game in Central Asia* (pp. 11–32). Lublin.
6. Fazilov, F., & Chen, X. (2013). China and Central Asia: A Significant New Energy Nexus. *The European Financial Review*, April–May.
7. Lahiri, B., & Masjidi, F. K. (2012). Landlocked Countries: A Way to Integrate with Coastal Economies. *Journal of Economic Integration*, 27(4), 505–519.
8. Irwin, D. A., & Terviö, M. (2002). Does Trade Raise Income? Evidence from the Twentieth Century. *Journal of International Economics*, 58(1), 1–18.
9. MacKellar, L., Wörgötter, A., & Wörz, J. (2000). Economic Development Problems of Landlocked Countries. *Transition Economics Series*, No. 14.
10. Shishkin, Ph. (2012). Central Asia's Crisis of Governance. *Asia Society*, January.
11. Olcott, M. B. (2011). Rivalry and Competition in Central Asia. In Hermann, W., & Linn, J. F. (Eds.), *Central Asia and the Caucasus: At the Crossroads of Eurasia in the 21st Century* (pp. 17–42).
12. Usmanova, H. (2018, February 12). Uzbekistan v blizhaishee vremia ne budet vstupat v Yevraziiski soiuz. Retrieved from [<http://eurasian-studies.org/archives/7082>].
13. Dow, D., & Karunaratna, A. (2006). Developing a Multidimensional Instrument to Measure Psychic Distance Stimuli. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 37, 578–602.
14. Metulini, R. (2013). Spatial Gravity Models for International Trade: A Panel Analysis among OECD Countries. *ERSA Conference Papers*, No. 13, p. 522. European Regional Science Association.
15. Kurečić, P. (2010). The New Great Game: Rivalry of Geostrategies and Geoeconomies in Central Asia. *Hrvatski Geografski Glasnik*, 21–48.

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